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Electoral Violence and Democratic Survival in Niger State Nigeria

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Abstract

This research critically examines the impact of electoral violence on democratic survival in Niger State, Nigeria. Despite the country's transition to democratic rule in 1999, electoral violence has remained a persistent threat, especially during general and local elections. This study aims to understand the causes, patterns, and consequences of electoral violence and how it influences democratic resilience in the state. The research adopts a qualitative methodology, employing semi-structured interviews with political actors, electoral officials, civil society representatives, community leaders, and victims of violence. It also includes content analysis of election monitoring reports, policy documents, newspaper articles, and INEC records. Findings indicate that electoral violence in Niger State is both systemic and strategic—often employed by political elites to gain advantage, intimidate opponents, and manipulate outcomes. Contributing factors include youth marginalization, politicization of ethnicity and religion, poor law enforcement, weak political institutions, and lack of accountability for perpetrators. The study finds that such violence not only disrupts electoral processes but also weakens democratic values such as transparency, citizen participation, and electoral credibility. Moreover, electoral violence has led to voter apathy, erosion of public trust in governance, and deepened political instability—threatening the long-term survival of democracy in the region. The study concludes that meaningful democratic

consolidation in Niger State requires proactive reforms: strengthening institutional capacity, promoting inclusive political engagement, enforcing electoral laws, and cultivating a culture of peaceful political participation. By highlighting the deep-rooted challenges and suggesting strategic interventions, this research contributes to the broader understanding of electoral violence in Nigeria and its implications for sustainable democracy.

Keywords: Electoral Process, Political Participation, Electoral Conflict, Political Instability, Democratic Survival

Introduction

Political Violence has been an enduring feature of human history and continues to affect many countries worldwide. This phenomenon is often a result of deep-rooted social, economic, and political tensions and can lead to significant consequences, including instability, loss of life, and disruption of governance structures.

Kaidor (2007) stated that throughout the 20th century, Latin America witnessed significant political violence, particularly in the form of military coups and authoritarian regimes. Countries like Argentina were marked by brutal military dictatorships, while guerrilla movements like the FARC in Colombia also used violence to advance their political agenda. The Chilean military coup of 1973 led to the overthrow of democratically elected President Salvador Allende and the rise of the military dictatorship of Augusto Pinochet, which involved mass political repression and violence. At other times, governments use force to defend their countries from outside invasions or other threats of force and to coerce other governments or conquer territory.

However, electoral violence has negative consequences for democratic culture; it affects the overall credibility of the democratic system, human security, and leads to wanton destruction of property. As a result of electoral violence, the capacity of governments to deliver social services like maintaining roads, providing electricity, water, schools, and healthcare systems has drastically reduced or is even completely nonexistent and ineffective (Machika, 2009).

With respect to the African continent, new democracies, especially since the 1990s, were termed the "third wave of democracy" and have been confronted with a series of electoral violence that has resulted in the killing and displacement of many innocent lives. Examples of these are noticeable in

Zimbabwe (2000, 2005, 2008), Zanzibar (2005, 2010), and Kenya (2007), among others (Chaturvedi, 2005; Khadiagala, 2008; Waki Report, 2008; and Usip, 2010).

Mahatma Gandhi was firmly opposed to political violence. He championed non-violence (Ahimsa) as the core of his political philosophy and strategy for resistance. His approach, called Satyagraha (truth-force), promoted peaceful civil disobedience to oppose injustice and colonial rule. Among his key points is rejection of political violence. Gandhi firmly believed that violence corrupts both the oppressor and the oppressed. Even in the face of injustice, he held that violence only continues the cycle of hatred and domination. Dalton (1993) argued that true change must come through peaceful means or it would not be lasting or moral.

Satyagraha (truth-force), this was Gandhi's unique method of non-violent resistance. Satyagraha means holding onto truth. He believed that through civil disobedience—refusing to obey unjust law without resorting to violence—oppressed people could weaken the conscience of their oppressors. It was about suffering willingly to show moral strength, not physical force. Ahimsa (non-violence) is a spiritual principle that became a political strategy under Gandhi. He saw non-violence not just as the absence of violence but as active love and compassion, even for one's enemy. It was central to all his movements and required inner discipline and moral courage. Moral stance, he argued, that the means used to achieve freedom must be as pure as the end. However, Gandhi criticized forms of violence that he opposed—violence in revolutions, even when their goals aligned with Indian Independence Gandhi (1927).

Nelson Mandela initially supported non-violence. Inspired by Gandhi's philosophy, especially during the early years of his activism with African National Congress (ANC).

In 1940–1950s, Mandela and the African National Congress (ANC) adopted non-violence resistance. Influenced by Mahatma Gandhi's legacy in South Africa, the ANC organized peaceful protests, boycotts, and strikes to challenge apartheid. This shows that while Mandela valued peace, he saw non-violence primarily as a strategic tool, not an unbreakable doctrine. However, shift to armed resistance after Sharpeville Massacre (1961) was a turning point. The killing of 69 unarmed protesters by police marked the end of any hope for peaceful protest under apartheid. The ANC was banned and peaceful activism was criminalized. Mandela said: "When the

government responded with violence to our peaceful protest, we had no choice but to reconsider our strategy." Nelson Mandela, Rivonia trial speech 1964: He co-founded UmKhonto we Sizwe (MK) in 1961, the ANC's armed wing which carried out sabotage against government installations, avoiding civilian casualties. Mentions he viewed violence as a last resort, according to the Rivonia trial speech (1994), that Mandela emphasized that this shift did not mean abandoning peace. It was a last resort in response to systematic violence: "I have cherished the ideal of a democratic and free society... it is an ideal for which I am prepared to die."

Notwithstanding, Frantz Fanon's view on violence: Fanon was a psychiatrist from Martinique who supported the Algerian independence movement. In his famous book *"The Wretched of the Earth"* (1961), he argued that colonialism is inherently violent—counter-violence by the oppressed is also so. He stated that violence is a cleansing force. Fanon believed violence was a necessary tool for the colonized to reclaim their identity, dignity, and freedom. That colonizer's domination is maintained by violence. Therefore, overthrowing it non-violently is nearly impossible.

Fanon (1961) supported the FLN (Front de Libération Nationale) in Algeria which used armed struggle against French colonizers. However, Jacques Chevallier (Algiers mayor) was a moderate French politician and Mayor of Algiers during the 1950s. He attempted peaceful reforms and dialogue with Algerians, but his efforts were blocked by both French hardliners and the intensifying violence of the war. He was removed from office in 1958 during the rising tension between the French army and Algerian independence fighters. Though not widely remembered like Fanon, Chevallier represents the failed moderate approach amidst rising revolutionary violence. Evans (2012). His fall from power marked the collapse of peaceful negotiations between colonizers and Algerians.

Since Nigeria returned to democratic rule in 1999 and engaged in other democratic processes, about eight (8) general elections have been conducted. These include the elections of 1999, 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, and most recently, 2023. However, it can be safely argued that none of these elections was free from violence, as contestants wanted to win at all costs, either by hook or by crook (Ogoyi & Obunkenmi, 2019).

According to Obakhedo (2011), the 1999 general election that brought President Olusegun Obasanjo to power was marred by widespread violence and fraud, as it was alleged to have been massively rigged in favor of the

People's Democratic Party (PDP). HRW (2003) also stated that the April and May 2003 elections witnessed the killing of about one hundred people and many more injured during federal and state elections in Nigeria.

Similarly, the 2007 election was equally marred by violence. According to the International Foundation for Electoral Systems (IFES) report (2007), there were about 967 incidents of electoral violence during the elections. Cases of abduction, killings, kidnapping, murder, protests, disruptions, intimidation, physical attacks, and poster defacing were all reported.

Closely related to that, the 2011 general election was among the worst instances of election-related violence since Nigeria's return to democracy in 1999. The violence started with widespread protests by supporters of the main opposition candidate, Muhammad Buhari, a Northern Muslim from the Congress for Progressive Change (CPC), following the re-election of incumbent Goodluck Jonathan, a Christian from the Niger Delta in the South, who was the candidate for the ruling People's Democratic Party (PDP).

However, the protests degenerated into violent riots and killings in the northern states of Adamawa, Bauchi, Gombe, Jigawa, Kaduna, and Kano, among others. Relief officials estimated that more than 6,500 people were displaced (Human Rights Watch, 2011).

According to the Nigerian Bar Association (NBA) Election Working Group Report (2019), there were several reports and live feeds of electoral violence from across the country. Party thugs and hoodlums had a field day invading voting centers to snatch and destroy voting materials, harass, molest, and intimidate voters. In some instances, suspected political thugs, accompanied by security operatives, hijacked and destroyed materials and interfered with the voting processes.

According to Höglund (2009). Political violence is a broad term that includes any use of force to achieve political goals, such as coups, assassinations, protests, insurgencies, and civil war. While electoral violence is a subset of political violence that specifically occurs during the electoral process including before, during, or after elections. It includes intimidation, ballot-snatching, attacks on voters or candidates, and rigging-related violence.

Relationship: Electoral violence is a form of political violence driven by competition for power. It often reflects deeper political instability, weak institutions, and lack of trust in the democratic process.

Niger State experienced significant electoral violence, including clashes between rival political party supporters, which led to confrontations that caused injuries and disrupted the electoral process in several areas, particularly in urban centers like Minna, Suleja, Kontagora, Lapai, Rijau, and Bida (HMR, 2020). Thus, this study aims to examine electoral violence and democratic survival in Niger State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Electoral violence in Niger State, Nigeria, poses a serious threat to the stability and survival of democracy. It undermines the credibility and integrity of the electoral process, disrupts economic activities, and escalates insecurity, thereby eroding public trust in democratic institutions and deterring citizen participation in elections.

Closely related to that, during a campaign in Suleja, for instance, hand-held explosives were thrown into the venue of the Niger East Senatorial campaign flag-off by unidentified persons, leading to the death of four people and causing serious injuries to many others.

According to IMG (2007), in Kontagora, Niger State, thousands of youths went on a rampage in the main town, destroying dozens of shops and vandalizing three churches. Major roads were barricaded, bonfires were set to disrupt vehicular movement, and about 47 suspects were arrested.

During the 2019 elections, Niger State experienced significant electoral violence, including clashes between rival political party supporters, which led to confrontations that caused injuries and disrupted the electoral process in several places, particularly in urban centers like Minna and Suleja (HMR, 2020). Similarly, local government elections in 2020 were marred by violence, with incidents of ballot snatching and voter intimidation in some polling units. Armed groups allegedly disrupted the voting process, leading to a low voter turnout.

Although various efforts have been made to curb electoral violence—such as electoral reforms, enhanced security measures during elections, and civic education campaigns—these strategies have proven ineffective, as those responsible for electoral violence are rarely held accountable, thus perpetuating the cycle of violence (PEV, 2020; IJASS, 2020).

Notwithstanding, institutional weaknesses, including inadequate funding and compromised law enforcement agencies, hinder the effective implementation of measures aimed at preventing electoral violence.

Research Questions

- i. To what extent has electoral violence impacted on citizens participation in elections in Niger State, Nigeria?
- ii. What are the challenges faced by authorities in addressing electoral violence in Niger State?

Objectives of the Study

- i. To evaluate the effects of electoral violence on citizen participations in the electoral process.
- ii. To explore the challenges faced by the authorities in addressing electoral violence in Niger state.

Conceptual Issues and Literature Review

Concept of Electoral Violence

Electoral Violence

In the context of elections, Iwu (2010) defined electoral violence as any act intended to disrupt the electoral process, intimidate voters, or manipulate the outcome of elections. It involves any random or organized act or threat of physical harm, blackmail, or abuse of political stakeholders in an attempt to determine, delay, or otherwise influence an electoral process.

In most cases, electoral violence is directed at electoral stakeholders, such as voters, candidates, party agents, election workers, media personnel, and election monitors. It may also target electoral information, such as registration data, vote results, ballots, and campaign materials (e.g., vehicles and public address systems), as well as electoral facilities, such as polling and counting stations. Additionally, electoral violence can disrupt electoral events, including campaign rallies (Hoglund, 2006).

Causes of Electoral Violence

The causes of electoral violence are complex and multi-faceted. According to Igbuzor (2009), electoral violence is driven by several factors, including greed, electoral abuses, election rigging, abuse of political power, alienation, marginalization, exclusion, and political economy of oil. Yet, other scholars adduce the following as the causes of the phenomenal: poverty/unemployment, ineffectiveness of security forces, culture of impunity, weak penalties, weak governance, corruption, proliferation of arms and ammunition (Galtung, 1969). In the same vein, other scholars argued that

the casual factors are: lack of security partnership of traditional rulers who are supposed to be the custodians of our cultural heritage; abuse of office by Electoral officials, zero - sum political or winner take it all syndrome; lucrative nature of political office; poor handling of election petition, and lack of faith in judiciary; lack of complain with the extent electoral law and enforcement of the enabling laws the partisan disposition of the police and poverty; corrupt INEC staff and ad- hoc officials who connive with the politicians and greed and selfish interest of politicians; conflict of interest between among politicians coupled with ideological bankruptcy (Ugiagbe, 2010).

Democracy

It is difficult to reach a consensus on the definition of democracy; however, the main idea of democracy is widely accepted to have been originated from Athens in the 6th Century BC. The Webster New Encyclopedia Dictionary (1993) defines democracy as a government in which supreme power is vested in the people and exercised by them (directly or indirectly) through representation. Larry Diamond (2004) gave an overview of what democracy is. He described democracy as a system of government with four key elements: A system for choosing and replacing the government through free and fair elections, active participation of the people as citizens in politics and civic life, protection of human rights of all citizens, and a rule of law in which the law and procedure apply equally to all citizens.

Furthermore, Kelsen (1955) and Barak (2006) asserted that representative democracy, which allows freedom of political expression, freedom of speech, and freedom of the press, are considered to be the essential rights that allow eligible citizens to be adequately informed and be able to vote according to their own interests.

Notwithstanding, Nassbaum (2000) sees democracy as the capacity of all voters to participate freely and fully in the life of their society, and that democracy is a form of government in which eligible citizens have equal rights and say in law-making (Diamond, 2004).

Democratic Survival

Democratic survival refers to the ability of democratic systems to endure and thrive despite various challenges and threats. There are many factors that contribute to democratic survival, such as:

The 1999 Constitution laid a foundation for democratic governance in Nigeria. This Constitution delineates the separation of powers among the executive, legislative, and judicial branches, providing checks and balances to prevent any single entity from dominating (Nwabueze, 1983). Furthermore, the 1999 Constitution includes provisions for human rights, freedom of speech, and other democratic values, which are essential for safeguarding the rights of citizens and fostering democratic norms (NIO, 2006).

Electoral reforms and institutions have been a crucial factor in Nigeria's democratic survival. The establishment of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) has contributed to the organization of relatively free and fair elections (Jinadu, 2012). While Nigeria has experienced election-related violence and fraud the role of (INEC) has gradually strengthened. For instance, the introduction of biometric voter registration in 2015 marked an essential step in reducing electoral fraud, signaling progress in improving electoral transparency.

In Nigeria, civil society organizations have played a vital role in supporting democracy by holding the government accountable, monitoring elections, and advocating for human rights. Organizations such as the Transition Monitoring Group (TMG) and the Centre for Democracy and Development (CDD) have monitored elections and exposed irregularities, putting pressure on government institutions to adhere to democratic principles (Akinboye, 2007). This vibrant civil society has created a culture of accountability, which is essential for sustaining democracy.

International organizations, foreign governments, and multinational organizations have also been instrumental in promoting democratic governance in Nigeria. The United Nations (UN), the African Union (AU), and the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) have been particularly active in Nigeria's democratic journey. The United States, United Kingdom, and European Union have provided funding, technical assistance, and political pressure to maintain Nigeria's democratic process. These international partnerships have contributed to strengthening democratic institutions and promoting good governance (Ajayi& Adejumbi, 2006).

Nigeria's media landscape has expanded in recent years, with digital media providing citizens with platforms to express their views and hold the government accountable. Social media platforms like Twitter, Facebook,

and WhatsApp have become vital tools for political discourse, amplifying citizens' voices and allowing for more transparent governance (Umechukwu, 2020). The #EndSARS protest of 2020, for instance, demonstrated the power of social media in mobilizing public opinion and promoting government accountability (Alamu, 2021). By facilitating information sharing and promoting civic engagement, digital media contributes to Nigeria's democratic survival.

Empirical Studies

In the course of this research. The empirical review is discussed in subsections in line with the research objectives.

The impact of electoral violence on citizen's participation in the electoral process: A study of Nigerian's 2015 and 2019 General Election: Adebayo (2021). The research applies political participation theory to understand the relationship between violence and citizen's decision to engage or obtain from electoral process. The study reveals that violence, including voter intimidation, ballot snatching, physical violence and vote-buying, particularly in rural areas discouraged active participations among certain segments of the population. The Government should provide securities both from Government and local vigilant to curb the menace.

Lawal (2020). The study adopts social movement theory, the nature of violence involves physical confrontations, political thuggery, disruption of polling units and voter intimidation. The study adopts mixed-method, the documentary and interview that involve electoral officials. The study examines how citizen's collective participation in elections is influenced by the presence of violence and political threats. The study identifies how fear of violence marginalized certain vulnerable groups, such as women and elderly, thus reducing the democratic inclusiveness of the process. The application of rule of laws and strengthening bureaucratic structures should be properly checked.

Musa (2020). The study adopts quantitative analysis using survey data, the study also makes use of apathy theory. The nature of violence involves voter's suppression, thuggery, destruction of ballot papers, and physical violence of polling station. The findings show that electoral violence created a sense of insecurity, leading to decreased voter turnout, particularly among women and youth. The study argues for comprehensive electoral reforms to improve voter confidence and participation. There should be collaboration

between the government, securities and other stakeholders in tackling the problem of thuggery and destruction of ballots papers.

Challenges of addressing electoral violence in Niger State: An analysis of the 2015 and 2019 elections: Adebayo (2020). The study found that poor coordination between security agencies, lack of political inability of authorities to effectively prevent or manage electoral violence. The study adopts institutional theory and makes use of qualitative case study approach. The study highlights that the involvement of political elites in fueling violence made it harder to ensure accountability and prevent recurrence of violence in subsequent election. In order to ensure accountability and prevent recurrence of violence, the rule of laws should be applied strictly.

Ibrahim (2018). The study found that while security agencies played a role in attempting to reduce violence, they were often over whelmed due to a lack of resources, personnel and coordination. The research adopts security sector reform (SSR) theory. The nature of the violence includes, political thuggery, violent protests, destruction of election materials classes between party supporter and vote-buying. The study emphasizes the need for reforms in the security sectors to improve then capacity to handle electoral violence. More security should be provided by the authorities.

Mohammed (2019) the study formed that lack of coordination, inadequate training for electoral officers to political pressure hindered efforts to address electoral violence. The natures of the violence involve ballot box snatching, electoral fraud, intimidation at polling stations, armed conflicts among political supporters, and adopt qualitative interviews and focus group discussion (FGD) a research method. The research calls for the stronger governance mechanisms and better accountability systems to improve the authorities' response to electoral violence. The Electoral official should be well trained and should be provided with necessary working materials in order to carry out their functions.

Research Gaps

Here are some possible research gap bases on the information provided in summary The possible gap based on Adebayo's (2021) statement on the impact of electoral violence on citizen participation in Niger state, Nigeria particularly focusing on the 2015 and 2019 general election could include the following: impact of electoral violence on women's political participation.

Although the study addresses voter intimidation and violence, the potential research gap could be the specific of electoral violence on woman's participation in the electoral process, are women more likely intimidated or coerced into abstaining from voting, and what measure can be taken to increase their participation in future elections? By addressing these gap, future research could provide a deeper understanding of the complexities surrounding electoral violence in Niger state. Lawal (2020), stated that the nature of violence involves physical confrontation, political thuggery, description of polling unit and voter intimidation. The possible research gap includes, how do women in Niger State experience or respond to electoral violence compared to men? However, Murtala (2020), in his statement, that the nature of violence involves voter suppression, thuggery, destruction of ballot papers. The possible research gap includes the impact of violence on the youth's participation in electoral process. How does violence such as voter suppression and political thuggery, affect the willingness of young people to engage in the political process? What are the barriers faced by youths and how can they be involve? Notwithstanding, Adebayo (2020), challenges of addressing electoral violence in Niger State: An analysis of 2015 and 2019. He stated that, the poor coordination between security agencies, lack of political inability of authorities to effectively prevent electoral violence. The possible research gaps are: how does electoral violence affect voter turnout, public trust in the election result and the legitimacy of elected officials and also, Ibrahim (2019), in his statement that the nature of the challenges is political thuggery, violence protest and the destruction of electoral materials. The possible research gap is exploring the specific impact of political thuggery on voter confidence and participation in the electoral process. Meanwhile, Mohammed (2019), in his study on the challenges faced in addressing electoral violence in Niger State, That the nature of the violence includes ballot box snatching, electoral fraud, intimidation of the polling station, the possible research gap is examining the specific impact of ballot box snatching and the integrity of the election and how it affects voter confidence.

Theoretical Framework

When examining the relationship between electoral violence and democratic survival in Niger State, Nigeria, several theories can be applied. The

political violence theory is one of the theories that align with the research topic:

Political Violence Theory

Political violence theory examines the motivations and conditions under which individuals or groups resort to violence to achieve political objectives. This theory encompasses various forms of violence and seeks to understand the underlying causes and dynamics that lead to such actions.

One of the most influential figures in this field is Ted Robert Gurr, who, in his work *Why Men Rebel* (1970), argued that political violence often stems from relative deprivation, when individuals or groups perceive a gap between their expectations and actual conditions. This perception can lead to frustration and, ultimately, violent actions as a means of expressing grievances or seeking change.

He also emphasized three levels of analysis:

1. ***Micro-level:*** Focuses on individual motivations and psychological factors that drive people to commit acts of violence.
2. ***Group-level:*** Examines how group dynamics, identity, and cohesion can lead to collective violence, particularly in contexts where groups feel threatened or marginalized.
3. ***Macro-level:*** Looks at broader societal and political structures, including state repression, political instability, and economic inequality, that create environments conducive to violence.

Relevance of Political Violence Theory to the Study

In the context of political violence, this theory helps explain how political competition, especially in fragile democracies, can escalate into violence. Factors such as political rivalry, ethnic tensions, and state repression can trigger violent incidents during elections, undermining democratic processes and threatening the stability of the political system.

Notwithstanding, people are not getting free, fair and credible elections since the fourth republic. The Youths in Niger State, on the other hand then took to aggressive behavior by destroying election material, snatching ballot boxes, killing some opposition parties manipulating election results. Base on this relevance the political violence theory is hereby adopted for the work.

Methodology

The researcher primarily utilizes a mixed-method approach, combining an interview and documentary research design, alongside the use of secondary data. This approach is suited for the examination of electoral violence, its impact, causes and the measures taken to ensure democratic survival in Niger State. The combination of qualitative interviews and documentary analysis brings a comprehensive understanding of the topic from both historical and first-hand perspectives. The population of this study comprises 15 participants who were purposively selected based on their direct involvement in or experience with electoral processes and incidents of electoral violence in Niger State. These include registered voters, electoral officials (INEC), security personnel, political party agents and civil society actors.

Documentary research involves (1) Government report: Independent National Electoral Commission/ Niger State Independent Electoral reports. Source: (INEC, NSIEC) official website. (2) NGO/ INGO report: Peacebuilding progress report by search for common ground. Source: search for common ground websites or office. (3) Journals and theses. A Journal articles on pre, main and post-election conflicts in Niger state and Nigeria. Source: JSTOR, goggles scholar, and university library. (4) Media publications. Newspaper articles on voter turnout in Niger State. Source: Daily trust, punch Newspaper, The guardian Nigeria. (5) Legal & policy documents. Nigeria Electoral Act 2022. Source: National Assembly and official Government gazette.

Data Presentation and Analysis

This section presents and analyzes data collected through qualitative interviews and document analysis. The data is organized thematically in line with the study's objectives. Each theme reflects recurring patterns drawn from participants' responses and relevant documents. Direct quotes (verbatim) and key findings are included to give voice to the participants and to support the analysis. This approach helps to uncover deeper insights into the nature, causes, and implications of electoral violence in Niger state, Nigeria .

Theme 1: Electoral violence impact on citizens' participation in elections in Niger State, Nigeria.

Source	Observe impact	Location m	Remark
INEC voter turnout report (2019)	30% voter turnout decline (in suleja LGA, electoral violence such as intimidation of voters contributed to low turnout)	Suleja/Bida	Compare to higher turnout in 2015; voters cited security fears
Clean foundation (2023)	48% fear violence, plan not to vote (the survey, conducted before the election, sample opinions across various LGAs including Minna, Bida, Suleja, and Kontagora)	General Niger state	From pre-election survey 2015 and 2019 incidents
Female voter	Stayed home due to past violence	Chanchaga LGA	Personal fear of base one previous attacks near polling units.
Male youth	Believes voting is unsafe	Bida LGA	Refuse to register for 2023 due to ballot box snatching in 2019

The data shows that electoral violence significantly discourages voter participation in Niger State. Documented evidence from INEC and Clean Foundation reveals a measurable drop in turnout, with over 30% decline in violence-prone areas like Suleja and Bida, and 48% of citizens expressing fear of voting due to potential violence.

Interview responses further validate this fear. A female voter from Chanchaga LGA admitted staying home due to previous threats, while a male youth in Bida stated that voting “is not worth risking his life”. This suggests a climate of fear and mistrust around elections, leading many to withdraw from the democratic process. This aligns with political violence

theory, which explains how perceived danger in politically unstable areas suppresses civic engagement and undermines electoral legitimacy.

Theme 2: Challenges faced by authorities in addressing electoral violence in Niger State

Source	Challenges Identify	Institution involved	Location	Remarks
CSO report (situation room) (2015)	Weak legal enforcement (citing failure to prosecute electoral offenders and lack of accountability for cancelled and rejected vote across many polling units)	Judiciary, police	State wide	Offenders often not prosecuted
INEC post-election review (2019)	Poor inter-agency coordination (Delays in security deployment and breakdown communication between INEC and security agencies which hinders timely response in electoral	INEC, police	General Niger	Affected pre-empty measure

violence in part
of Niger State

Nigeria police report (2023)	Inadequate manpower and logistic (citing shortage of officers and vehicle during the 2023 elections in Niger state)	police	State wide	Slow respond time
police officer	Late response due to resource constraints	Police	Minna	Lack of mobility during crises
INEC official	Consequences for offenders	INEC, judiciary	Kontagora, and Bida	Frustration over repeated violence

The findings reveal that structural, legal, and resource-based challenges significantly hinder authorities in managing electoral violence in Niger State. The police face manpower shortages and logistical difficulties, leading to delayed responses, as seen in Minna. The INEC post-election review and CSO reports also point to poor inter-agency coordination and weak legal enforcement, which create loopholes that offenders exploit. Interview responses from field officers reinforce these issues. A police officer admitted

that "they often arrive after violence has occurred", while an INEC official Kontagora and Bida highlighted "the lack of consequences for offenders", leading to frustration and repeated cycles of violence. These challenges point to institutional weaknesses in Nigeria's electoral security framework. Without addressing these systemic issues, effective violence prevention and electoral integrity remain difficult to achieve.

Discussions of Findings

The findings from interviews and document analysis, interpreting them through the lens of Political Violence Theory and comparing them with existing literature on electoral violence and democratic survival in Nigeria, especially Niger State.

The study found that electoral violence significantly reduces citizens' willingness to vote, particularly in areas with a history of violence. Respondents consistently expressed fear and distrust in the process, with many choosing to stay away from polling units. This supports Adebayo (2018) and CLEEN Foundation (2023), who noted that voter apathy increases in violence-prone regions. According to Political Violence Theory, such violence is not incidental but strategic—used by political actors to suppress opposition turnout or instill fear, thereby manipulating electoral outcomes without outright rigging. This view supports Okoye (2020), who argued that the political class benefits from weak enforcement, ensuring that electoral violence remains a viable tool. In Niger State, the failure to prosecute offenders and late responses to violence reflect not just weakness—but tolerance or exploitation of the system by powerful actors.

Challenges Authorities Face in addressing Electoral violence in Niger state. The study revealed that authorities, (security agencies and INEC officials) in Niger state struggle with the limited manpower, logistics, lack of coordination, and weak enforcement of electoral laws. While these may appear as institutional shortcomings, Political Violence Theory helps explain why such weaknesses persist. Political elites may deliberately weaken enforcement democratic actors can operate with impunity. In Niger State, reduced turnout in Suleja, Bida, and Chanchaga aligns with this logic. Violence becomes a tool for power preservation, undermining democratic participation. While these are logistical issues on the surface, Political Violence Theory suggests deeper political roots: political elites may intentionally under- resource enforcement agencies or manipulate

security arrangements to favor certain interests to maintain control over the electoral process and allow violence to serve their interests with little consequence. This aligns with the view of Oberschall (2007), who argues that political violence thrives where state institutions are either complicit or ineffective, creating a space where democracy will have destruction.

Conclusion

The study concludes that electoral violence in Niger State is a calculated political tool employed to influence electoral outcomes and maintain political power. Grounded in Political Violence Theory, the findings demonstrate that violence is used not just as a disruptive force, but as an instrument of electoral strategy, especially where democratic institutions are weak or compromised. This cycle of violence undermines the integrity of elections, discourages voter participation, and delegitimizes democratic governance. If unaddressed, it threatens long-term democratic survival in Nigeria, making elections more about power struggles than public choice. To safeguard Nigeria's democracy, electoral violence must be addressed as both a political and institutional failure, requiring coordinated reforms across legal, security, and political systems.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. ***Strengthen Legal Enforcement:*** Government and INEC must ensure timely arrest and prosecution of electoral offenders to end impunity.
2. ***Improve Electoral Security:*** Security agencies should be adequately trained, equipped, and deployed early, with non-partisan oversight.
3. ***Youth Engagement and Empowerment:*** State and federal governments should invest in job creation, education, and political inclusion to prevent youth exploitation by politicians.
4. ***Regulate Political Parties:*** INEC should enforce internal democracy within parties and sanction those found sponsoring violence.
5. ***Voter and Civic Education:*** Continuous education campaigns are needed to sensitize citizens on peaceful participation and the dangers of violence.
6. ***Enhance INEC's Independence:*** Legal and financial autonomy for INEC should be prioritized to insulate it from political manipulation.

7. **Promote Political Dialogue and Peace Accords:** Political parties should commit to peaceful conduct through binding pre-election peace agreements monitored by civil society.

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